

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE D1.5 Initial Gender Transformative Approach

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List of acronyms

CNS: Close-to-Nature Silviculture

COP: Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

DRR: Disaster Risk Reduction

EC: European Commission

EIGE: European Institute for Gender Equality

EU: European Union

EEB: European Environmental Bureau

FAO Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

CGIAR: Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research

GTA: Gender Transformative Approach

ILO: International Labour Organization

IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

LGBTQI: Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer, Intersex

MEL: Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning System

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

R&C: Regions and Communities

R&I: Research and Innovation

REA: European Executive Research Agency

UN Women: United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women

UN: United Nations

UNECE: United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

UNFPA: United Nations Population Fund

UNICEF: United Nations Children's Fund

UNPRPD: United Nations Partnership on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities

WECF: Women Engage for a Common Future

WP: Work Package

Project information

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Acronym: FARCLIMATE

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List of participants:

Partner No.	Organisation Name Acronym
1 (Coord.)	UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO UVIGO
2	CONTACTICA S.L. CTA
3	INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURE IUCN
4	C4G - CONSULTING AND TRAINING NETWORK, LDA C4G
5	INVIALE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L. INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION GGG
8	UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE ULIEGE
9	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCIÓN FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN CESEFOR
10	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA UNL
11	FUNDACIÓN PARA LA PESCA Y MARISQUEO FUNDAMAR FUNDAMAR
12	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW ENoLL
13	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS CERTH
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Deliverable details

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Abstract:	<p>This document describes the Gender Transformative Approach (GTA) of FARCLIMATE. To effectively combat climate change, interventions must incorporate gender transformation, which involves redefining gender roles, opportunities, relationships, and agency within broader societal and environmental changes. Drawing from existing programs, the GTA of FARCLIMATE aims to ensure that all project activities promote gender transformation. This includes understanding and challenging gender norms, ensuring equitable access and control, involving all genders in decision-making, and monitoring progress throughout implementation. The GTA will undergo a continuous process of interaction and exchange during the project's implementation, and a final version (D1.6), incorporating project learnings, will be delivered at the end of the project (M48).</p>

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Draft_V0.1	10/04/2024	First draft
Draft_V0.2	28/05/2024	Second draft
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1 Executive Summary

This document presents the **initial version** of the **Gender Transformative Approach (GTA)**, which constitutes a **living document** that will undergo a continuous process of **interaction** and **exchange** during the project's implementation. A **final version (D1.6)**, incorporating project learnings, will be delivered at the end of the project (**M48**).

FARCLIMATE is strongly committed to **challenging** and **transforming** existing **gender** norms, roles, and power dynamics to achieve greater **gender equality**. As part of WP1 (project management), task **T1.5** is devoted to implementing a gender transformative program, which will lead to an in-depth understanding of the needs, behaviours, and attitudes of all genders, the influence of socioeconomic factors, and **will help researchers question gender norms** and **stereotypes** and rethink standards and reference models.

Section 2, of an **introductory** nature, summarizes the significant challenges and the work program of FARCLIMATE, as well as the **purpose** of this document: to present the **harmonized framework** for gender transformation within the project, describing the guidelines that establish the fundamental aspects, criteria, conceptual foundations, and processes that the various activities must consider.

Section 3 is structured into four thematic blocks:

- **Understanding Key Gender Concepts:** description of definitions and key milestones, as well as the relevance of covering gender and adaptation in both the Global North and South.
- **Why Gender Transformation?:** introduction to gender transformative approaches (GTAs), which represent a shift in how we think about and approach gender.
- **Climate Change is not Gender-Neutral:** the importance of a gender perspective in climate change and adaptation and its consequences in terms of impact in the European context.
- **How are the gender aspects and dimensions being addressed in EU climate policies?:** brief description of some key elements for designing effective and just climate policies and measures, and analysis of the context and climate policies in the EU.

Section 4 focuses on the **Gender Transformative FARCLIMATE Project Design and Implementation**. After a description of the integration of gender in project objectives and the consortium capacities and experience, the **guidelines** and **directives** that must be considered in the project's implementation are summarized. **Monitoring** and **evaluation** of these guidelines will be subsequently addressed in **Section 5**.

Section 6 synthesizes the **conclusions** and **recommendations** of this initial phase of the GTA, which will be reviewed and updated as implementation progresses. Finally, **supplementary documentation** included with this document comprises a glossary of **gender-related terms**, a summary of international gender-specific environmental and climate **commitments**, and a list of **additional resources** and references for gender transformation and climate adaptation.

2 Introduction

All human and environmental systems **adapt to climate** and its **natural variations**. Adaptation to **human-induced changes** in climate has typically been viewed as incremental adjustments aimed at preventing disruptions to systems in their current locations. However, in certain places and for certain systems, vulnerabilities and risks may be so significant that they require **transformational** rather than incremental adaptations (Kates et al., 2012).

Human societies are not uniform entities; therefore, it is crucial to consider the roles of class, race, caste, gender, and other factors for meaningful and effective inclusion. **Gender** greatly influences the planning and outcomes of adaptation efforts. As we transition from science-centred theories to incorporating socially acceptable and relatable goals in adaptation strategies, it becomes essential to recognize the importance of understanding the **heterogeneity** within human societies and its implications. Gender, as a significant contributor to this heterogeneity, warrants detailed consideration and study. The linkage between gender and climate adaptation carries social and cultural implications that must be acknowledged and integrated into policy and practice.

The FARCLIMATE project tackles the intricate challenges of developing and expanding **climate-resilient measures**, with a focus on making them accessible and **comprehensible to all**, while also addressing the prevalent social, political, and economic barriers. FARCLIMATE initiatives will be deployed in a minimum of 20 regions and communities across Europe, serving as case studies where transformative solutions toward climate resilience will be pursued. The project will engage a wide array of stakeholders, including regional and local governments, the private sector, civil society, social partners, academia, industries, and other relevant actors. Additionally, it will target three key sectors affected by climate change—agriculture, forestry, and fisheries.

Figure 1. Graphical abstract of FARCLIMATE Project

To face this significant challenge, FARCLIMATE has outlined the following work program:

- Initial **engagement** with all pertinent **stakeholders** in each region to establish management mechanisms.
- Establishment of **living labs** for collaborative creation, testing, and upscaling of innovative activities in real-world settings.
- In-depth **research** on the primary value chains, socioeconomic and environmental characteristics, and existing economic sectors of all investigated **regions and communities** through monitored indicators.
- Implementation of **cross-cutting actions** across all case studies, including tailored training activities for community empowerment, targeting various stakeholders and focusing on climate change and related hazards and risks.
- Deployment of technically and socially viable **innovative solutions** in the **agriculture, forestry, and fisheries** sectors to enhance their capacity to adapt to climate change impacts. Nature-based solutions will underpin FARCLIMATE's innovative endeavours.
- Development of **diverse tools** to disseminate insights, identified barriers, and successful outcomes from FARCLIMATE, including policy recommendations, guidelines, management plans, and the innovative Transformation Hub.

FARCLIMATE is firmly committed to challenging and transforming existing gender norms, roles, and power dynamics to achieve greater gender equality. Within WP1 (project management), task T1.5 is dedicated to implementing a **gender transformative** program, which will lead to an in-depth understanding of genders' needs, behaviours and attitudes, and the influence of socioeconomic factors, and will help researchers question gender norms and stereotypes and rethink standards and reference models.

Drawing from insights gleaned from existing gender-transformative adaptation programs and experiences, this task will ensure that all project activities and influences adhere to and promote best practices conducive to gender transformation. This commitment extends to the activities across the eight WPs as well as the 20 case studies within FARCLIMATE.

Thinking about the role of a gender transformative approach (GTA) requires the consortium to **honestly self-reflect** and assess their **openness** and **preparedness** to facilitate **systemic change**. By definition, GTAs mean change for the implementing organizations and how they work.

The purpose of this document is to present the **harmonized framework** for gender transformation within the project, describing the **guidelines** that establish the fundamental aspects, criteria, conceptual foundations, and **processes** that the various activities must consider. Starting with a brief description of the concepts, key milestones, and challenges of the current scenario in relation to gender in the context of climate adaptation, the following sections outline the main characteristics of the GTA of FARCLIMATE, from project design to project implementation, as well as the system designed for monitoring, evaluation, and learning.

3 Gender in Climate Context

3.1 Understanding Key Gender Concepts

Gender equality, a fundamental **human right** recognized globally, requires addressing systemic barriers alongside legal reforms. This includes challenging gender stereotypes, bridging gaps, and combating violence against women, all pivotal for achieving **Sustainable Development Goals**. Integrating the gender perspective across sectors is essential for fostering fairness and social justice, echoing human rights principles. Embracing gender equality in research and innovation, as emphasized by the European Research Executive Agency, is key for inclusive progress (REA, 2023):

“Understanding how gender plays a vital role in research and innovation allows us to address the diverse needs of citizens of the European Union. It enhances the societal relevance of the knowledge, technologies and innovations produced, and contributes to the production of greater goods and services”.

3.1.1 Definitions and Key Milestones

As part of the European Commission **Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025** (European Commission, 2020a), which outlines the Commission's broader commitment to equality across all EU policies, the European Commission is dedicated to promoting **gender equality in research and innovation**. In this regard, it is worth noting that Horizon 2020 was the first framework programme to prioritize gender as a cross-cutting issue, with one of its underlying objectives being the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content, resulting in an increased number of "gender-flagged" topics across the programme. Horizon Europe goes even further by mandating the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation (R&I) content by default, unless the topic description explicitly states otherwise.

Gender equality provisions in **Horizon Europe** encompass both gender balance and gender dimension, defined as follows¹:

- **Gender balance** refers to achieving an equitable distribution of women and men in research teams responsible for project implementation. Horizon Europe projects are expected to strive for a balanced, 50/50 participation rate of both genders within teams and leadership roles. Notably, gender balance among researchers is a key evaluation criterion for proposals with similar scores in Horizon Europe.
- The **gender dimension** implies analysing and taking into account the possible differences between men and women (biological characteristics as well as the social and cultural features), boys and girls, or males and females, in the R&I content of the project. Integrating this gender dimension is now a mandatory requirement in all research and innovation projects across Horizon Europe, unless a topic explicitly specifies otherwise.

The EU's “Gendered Innovations 2: Inclusive Analysis for Research and Innovation” report (European Commission, 2020b), produced by the EU funded Horizon 2020 expert group on ‘Gendered Innovations’, provides researchers and innovators with **methodological tools** for sex, gender and intersectional analysis, with concrete case studies in fields of relevance for Horizon Europe. FARCLIMATE's GTA leverages these resources, advancing its **transformative agenda**. Understanding the EU's approach to gender inequalities and terminology is crucial for establishing **a common understanding** among project partners and ensuring equal

¹ For a more detailed description, see *Gender equality in research and innovation. Achieving gender equality in research, how it relates to the European Research Area, networks and news*. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en#gender-equality-in-horizon-europe

comprehension of the core concepts related to the human right to equality. **Annex 1** provides a comprehensive **Glossary of gender-related terms**, drawing from relevant sources (UNPRPD, 2023; UNICEF, 2021; EIGE, 2012), to support a transformative gender perspective.

As a complement to the aforementioned glossary, **Annex 2** includes an overview of **international gender-specific environmental and climate commitments**, reflecting the gradual incorporation of a gender perspective internationally. From the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) in 1979 -the first international bill of women's rights addressing rural development, resources, credit, education, the right to work, and participation- to COP28 in Dubai in 2023, much progress has been made. During COP28's Gender Equality Day, the COP28 Presidency launched the Gender-Responsive Just Transitions & Climate Action Partnership, endorsed by 68 Parties. The Partnership includes commitments on finance, data, and equal opportunities, building on progress from the UN Climate Change Lima Work Programme and its Gender Action Plan. Additionally, on the eve of COP28, the Global Conference on Gender and Environmental Data called for increased collection and use of gender and environmental data to advance gender-responsive climate and environmental action globally.

3.1.2 An Issue of Life or Death, Not Just in The Global South

The effects of climate change are and will be felt by all, but they will not impact everyone equally. Those who are **vulnerable** and **marginalized**, with limited access to resources and assets, are already experiencing the consequences more severely and encountering formidable **barriers** in adapting to climate change.

The team of the Background Paper for the 2019 report of the Global Commission on Adaptation conducted a review of relevant peer-reviewed research and grey literature on gender and climate change adaptation emerging over the last decade, covering gender and adaptation in both the **Global North and South** (Resurrección et al., 2019). When presenting the conclusions of their work, the authors clarify that these focus on adaptation contexts in the Global South largely due to the **availability of literature**. Centring attention on the Global South is a common feature of the work undertaken by the growing critical mass of multilateral and bilateral agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), governments, etc., which are seeking ways to achieve profound and sustainable development objectives by addressing the root causes of gender inequality. This could lead to the **misconception** that the situation in contexts such as **Europe**, a global leader in gender equality -14 of the top 20 countries worldwide in terms of gender equality are EU Member States- does not require prioritizing equality as a key action. Nothing could be further from the truth.

A clear example reflecting the challenges in the current situation in the European context can be found in the development of **standards**. Standards, which should be gender-neutral, are often developed for a reference individual based on a Caucasian man aged 25-30, weighing 70 kg (Criado-Perez, 2019). The **lack of gender-responsiveness** in standardization is a matter of **life and death** (UNECE, 2022). Women are 73% more likely than men to be killed in a car accident because crash test dummies are based on male anthropometry (Forman et al., 2019). A cross-country analysis across 99 countries found that standards are associated with a reduction in unintentional fatalities for men, but women are not reaping the same benefits from standardization (Parkouda, 2020).

Certain technologies may **impact** individuals differently based on **gender disparities**. The digital sphere remains largely male-dominated, inadvertently producing research outcomes that fail to empower women and girls (UNECE, 2023). For instance, artificial intelligence, capable of autonomous learning from various sources, may inadvertently develop biases against women or gender minorities.

Gender **stereotypes** place constraints on life choices, education and employment options. In turn, these constraints perpetuate stereotypes and more broadly, unequal gender power relations in the public and

private sphere (European Commission, 2024). Gender-based **violence**, in all its forms, remains under-reported and overlooked, both inside and outside the EU (European Commission, 2020a).

Figure 2. Gender stereotypes and gender-based violence data in the EU. Source: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 (European Commission, 2020a).

Organizations such as The World Bank and the World Trade Organization have repeatedly emphasized that women and girls constitute half of the world's population's potential, and narrowing the gender gap will foster **economic development** (World Bank and WTO, 2020). It's not only women who bear the brunt of the absence of gender responsiveness. Failing to safeguard and encourage the contributions of women diminishes families, businesses, and countries alike.

In the EU **labour market**, gender segregation across both sectors and occupations has remained stable since 2019, with very tiny reductions in 2022. Strong correlations are observed between gender **segregation** in economic sectors on the one hand and occupations on the other: In countries where sectoral gender segregation is high, gender occupational segregation also tends to be high. National policies addressing gender segregation in economic sectors, occupations and education most commonly target sectors with stronger technical content, basically STEM and ICT activities, which tend to have higher levels of pay; education, health and welfare sectors are not addressed by policies as often. However, women graduates in the EU ICT sector were less than 2 % of female graduates, increasing only 0.6 percentage points between 2013 and 2021.

Figure 3. Women's employment data in the EU. Source: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 (European Commission, 2020a).

Ultimately, we can confirm that the women’s employment rate in the EU is higher today than ever before, but many women still face significant barriers to entering and staying in the labour market. This becomes particularly critical when there is the **intersection** of gender with additional conditions of vulnerability or marginalization, such as belonging to an ethnic or religious minority or having a migrant background.

3.2 Why Gender Transformation?

Gender transformative approaches (GTAs) represent a **shift in how we think** about and approach gender. While "business-as-usual" accommodative gender approaches try to work around barriers, often focusing solely on women, gender transformative approaches have broken new ground by transforming structural barriers and **challenging gender norms**. These norms entail the unwritten rules about who can do what kind of work, control what types of assets, and make what level of decisions. These approaches are operationalized through context-appropriate, locally led, and constructive strategies.

Figure 4. Conceptual Framework for Gender Transformative Programming. Source: Adapted from UNFPA (2023).

Since 2012, scientists at WorldFish and their partners have led the conceptualization, testing, and scaling of gender-transformative approaches within the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR), focusing on aquaculture, fisheries, agriculture, and broader development sectors. As defined by CGIAR, a GTA to development goes **beyond addressing the "symptoms"** of gender inequality to target the social norms, attitudes, behaviours, and social systems that underlie them. GTAs aim to move beyond individual self-improvement among women and towards transforming the **power dynamics** and **structures** that perpetuate gendered inequalities (CARE, 2015). These inequalities can be examined across three deeply interconnected dimensions (Morgan, 2014):

- **Agency:** individual or collective capacities (knowledge and skills), attitudes, critical reflection, assets, actions, and access to services.
- **Relational** (intrahousehold and beyond): the expectations and cooperative or negotiation dynamics embedded within relationships between people in the home, market, community, and groups and organizations.
- **Structural:** informal and formal institutional rules and practices (environment, norms, recognition and status).

To apply a GTA in practice, the first step is to acknowledge that integrating gender into policies, programs, and activities is a **process**. GTA serves as a lens that enables us to identify the most effective strategies for implementing an intervention across the **gender continuum**, with the aim of transforming gender norms and power relations in each specific context where we operate (European Commission, 2023).

Figure 5. Gender Integration Continuum. Source: Adapted from UNFPA (2023).

The development impacts of gender inequality are well-documented, and as we mentioned in the previous section, there is ample literature regarding the GTA framework and its application to programs and experiences in the **Global South**. However, it is worth noting a **lack of empirical evidence** about outcomes from gender transformative approaches in the **Global North**. In addition to the review conducted by Resurrección et al. (2019) to inform the Global Commission on Adaptation, the following references have been selected as they are considered relevant to the scope of the FARCLIMATE project:

- The report "Gender Transformative Approaches for Food Security, Improved Nutrition, and Sustainable Agriculture - A Compendium of Fifteen Good Practices" (FAO, IFAD, and WFP, 2020) describes 15 GTA approaches, primarily in Africa and Asia, with less presence in Latin America.
- The CGIAR Collaborative Platform for Gender Research report "Implementing Gender Transformative Approaches in Agriculture" (GGIAR, 2019), prepared as a Discussion Paper for the European

Commission, discusses frameworks, methodologies, and tools used in GTAs. Project implementation references are limited, as in the previous case, to the African and Asian continents, with less presence in Latin America.

- Deering's paper "Gender- Transformative Adaptation. From Good Practice to Better Policy" (2019), published by CARE, draws on experience and learning from 10 projects implemented by various development actors interested in gender transformation in adaptation in Africa and Asia.

In light of the analysis of experiences and available documentation, we can affirm that the introduction of GTAs in the field of climate adaptation is a clear example of the potential of South-North cooperation, from which Europe can extract valuable lessons by looking at other geographies.

3.3 Climate Change is not Gender-Neutral

3.3.1 The importance of a gender perspective in climate change and adaptation

The **global climate crisis, environmental degradation, biodiversity loss, and gender inequality** rank among the world's most intricate and urgent issues, each presenting multi-dimensional challenges and pervasive implications. These four challenges intertwine, compounding risks and threats for all (OECD, 2023).

Figure 6. The Gender-Climate-Biodiversity/Environment Intersection. Source: OECD (2023).

There is already a vast body of academic and policy literature identifying gender inequalities arising from processes that harm the environment and climate, such as climate change and pollution. This literature emphasizes that the different roles traditionally assigned to men and women in relation to the environment, as well as existing structural (systemic) norms, often lead to discrimination and create obstacles to women's access to resources and means that would allow them to manage and adapt to the situation (European Parliament, 2012).

The effects of climate change have a **universal reach**, affecting people in every country worldwide. However, its **impacts vary** depending on the living conditions of each society. In this context, marginalized and vulnerable

sectors will suffer more profound impacts and will have a lower capacity for adaptation. Within these population sectors, women and girls are most affected due to the naturalization of gender roles, which teach them to be passive agents within their communities, focusing on household and family care tasks without participating in the public sphere. Undoubtedly, **climate change is not gender-neutral**. It is now widely recognized that environment-related risks and threats are not gender-neutral; on the contrary, women and girls are disproportionately affected by climate change, environmental degradation, and biodiversity loss (UN Women, 2022). In addition, gender considerations often intersect with other social, physical, and geographical factors, making those at the intersections most at risk. According to UN Women, climate change is a “**threat multiplier**”, which escalates social, political, and economic tensions in fragile and conflict-affected settings. When disaster strikes, women are less likely to survive and more likely to be injured due to longstanding gender inequalities that have created disparities in information, mobility, decision-making, and access to resources and training.

Climate action seeks coherence between international mechanisms that advance women's rights and gender equality and those related to climate change. It is acknowledged that barriers to the exercise of the rights of women and LGBTI persons also represent limitations in achieving GHG reduction targets and building adaptive capacity.

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (**UNFCCC**), the highest decision-making body for climate change, identifies **gender equality** as one of the transversal and independent variables that must be considered in the design and implementation of national climate change strategies and action plans. The **Paris Agreement** also emphasizes that adaptation actions should be **gender-responsive** and follow country-driven, participatory, and transparent approaches (Global Commission on Adaptation, 2019). Findings from the literature review indicate that there is a substantial volume of literature on intersectionality, demonstrating an increased awareness of the benefits of simultaneously addressing climate, environment, biodiversity, and gender equality. However, gaps in information on how to operationalize this hinder effective collaborative action, including in development cooperation.

3.3.2 A loss of talent, effectiveness, and efficiency

In the EU, the underrepresentation of women in the green economy, both in employment and decision-making, is not only a reflection of injustice but also results in a loss of talent, effectiveness, and efficiency in the goal of improving the environment, further exacerbating gender gaps. Environmental issues are often centred on technology and science, but the importance of human aspects, including gender, is gaining recognition not only for ethical reasons but also for pragmatic ones. This is because when the gender perspective is integrated into environmental policies or programs, their effectiveness increases.

As mentioned earlier, the importance of including the gender perspective in environmental projects can be summarized by the fact that environmental degradation, on one hand, and policies related to the environment, climate change, and the transition toward a sustainable economy, on the other, have different impacts on women and men. Moreover, women face roles and stereotypes, such as those related to caring for children and other dependents, which influence their position in the economy and the job market.

In particular (Fundación Biodiversidad, 2022):

1. Women might find it more difficult to (re)enter green jobs because they often lack adequate technical training, making them underrepresented in science and technology-intensive sectors, where there's often a shortage of specialists. Gender stereotypes regarding the roles of women and men can deter women from pursuing such jobs and/or prevent men from considering them as equals in these fields.

2. **The time women spend caring for dependents is far greater** than that spent by men, affecting their position in society and, specifically, in the green economy and green jobs. This often limits their availability for green employment or entrepreneurship due to family responsibilities.

3. **Entrepreneurship has an empowering effect and increases women's agency, turning them into agents of change for sustainability.** Women's entrepreneurship in the green economy and, more broadly, in the transition toward environmental and social sustainability is a path that contributes to enhancing women's capacity to make decisions and participate in employment and the economy on equal terms.

4. **The transition from a linear to a circular economy involves systemic transformations.** These transformations will not be possible if women do not participate equally in strategic decision-making for this transition, in businesses, employment, education, and the adoption of new social and cultural values. Translating those strategic decisions into policies and projects that foster behavioural changes must also be done by and for women in conditions of equality; otherwise, it will not be effective.

5. **Men and women have different consumption patterns.** A key aspect of sustainability, including the circular economy, is transforming our consumption patterns, which are considered unsustainable. Regardless of socio-economic level, women demonstrate a greater predisposition toward environmental conservation, for example, by using less private transportation and more public transportation, or by using energy more. Additionally, a significant percentage of household consumption decisions fall on women, making it imperative to incorporate their sensitivities, needs, and preferences into any project aimed at environmental conservation and climate change adaptation.

Inequalities between women and men are systemic, meaning they are a fundamental part of the systems in which they operate. This is why they are so difficult to eliminate. In the environmental field, there are examples of systemic inequalities between women and men, which can be found in systems such as agri-food, forestry, and fisheries. In these systems, women's participation in decision-making, ownership of production means, employment, and power relations is limited. This restricts the possibilities for systemic transformations that could enable real progress toward genuine equality in treatment and opportunities between women and men.

By integrating a gender perspective into all actions aimed at combating climate change, a more accurate and respectful understanding is achieved of the differing realities faced by men, women, and gender-diverse groups, as well as their unequal relationships in terms of access, use, and control of resources. This approach helps identify gender roles and gaps, where climate change initiatives and measures can intervene positively, reducing structural inequalities and promoting fair participation and distribution of benefits.

3.4 How are the gender aspects and dimensions being addressed in EU climate policies?

3.4.1 Some key elements to designing effective and just climate policies and measures

Since the publication of "The Training Manual on Gender and Climate Change" (Aguilar, 2009), designed by the Global Gender and Climate Alliance (GGCA) as a practical tool to enhance the capacity of policy and decision makers in developing gender-responsive climate change policies and strategies, efforts to provide essential knowledge and concrete guidance to key actors on how their actions on climate change can better address the needs of women and men in developing countries have been increasing. However, reflections, recommendations, and actions aimed at contexts such as Europe have been rather scarce. To design effective and just climate policies and measures, it is necessary to invest more effort into examining the underlying reasons for gender differences, incorporating an intersectional approach. Gotelind Alber categorizes these differences into four main axes (EEB and WECF, 2021): Carbon Footprints, Impacts and Vulnerability, Response at the Individual Level, and Policy Response.

Gender Differentials in Carbon Footprints

- Women generally have lower carbon footprints than men, partly due to lower average incomes and consumption levels.
- Single men in Europe have larger carbon footprints than single women, mainly due to differences in mobility and dietary habits.
- In the UK, female-headed households and ethnic minorities have smaller carbon footprints than male-headed and white households, primarily because of lower indirect emissions.
- Men's jobs are often more carbon-intensive compared to the sectors where women are the majority, such as service, education, and care.

Impacts and Vulnerability

- Women and girls are disproportionately affected by climate change impacts, such as droughts, floods, and heatwaves, due to structural disadvantages and poorer access to resources.
- Women are more exposed to heatwaves because they often live in less well-insulated buildings and have lower incomes.
- Natural disasters often increase women's workloads and expose them to higher risks of sexual violence.
- Evidence from events like Hurricane Katrina shows that race, class, and gender intersect to create disproportionate impacts.

Response at Individual Level

- Women are generally more concerned about climate change and willing to adopt sustainable behaviours but face barriers like specific needs for comfort and safety.
- The Fridays for Future movement, dominated by young women, exemplifies gendered concerns about climate change.

Policy Response

- Climate policies can have different impacts on genders due to income disparities and labour divisions.
- Some policies, such as carbon taxes, can disproportionately affect low-income individuals, particularly women.

The analysis of the main drivers of gender inequality, as well as spheres of life that are particularly important for gender relations in the context of climate policy, can be synthesized into the following dimensions:

Symbolic Order: Social hierarchies and power relations create and perpetuate gender disparities.

Institutionalized Androcentrism: Systems and institutions are often biased towards masculinity, affecting problem definitions and strategies.

Gender Representation: Women are underrepresented in decision-making processes related to climate policy.

Care Economy: Women disproportionately perform unpaid care work, affecting how climate measures impact their daily lives.

Market Economy: Women are underrepresented in climate-relevant sectors and often earn less, making economic instruments like CO2 pricing more burdensome for them.

Public Resources and Infrastructures: Women's lower emissions are linked to their mobility behaviours, highlighting the need for accessible public infrastructures.

Body, Health, and Safety: Gender norms and physical differences affect how men and women experience climate impacts and adaptation measures.

3.4.2 A brief analysis of the context and climate policies in the EU

The report 'Review of the Implementation in the EU of Area K of the Beijing Platform for Action: Women and the Environment Gender Equality and Climate Change' (IEGE, 2012) was the first EU-wide report on **gender equality and climate change**, providing comparable **data at the EU level**. Furthermore, it introduced the first indicators to support policymakers in measuring progress in climate change policies from the perspective of gender equality. More than a decade later, statistics on women and men in key decision-making positions with competencies in environment and climate change indicate that the average participation rates of women have increased from **19.2%** in **2012** to **29.7%** in **2023**. However, the gap between men and women remains very significant.

The **EU Climate Law**, a cornerstone of the European Green Deal, commits the EU to achieving climate neutrality by 2050 and reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. While gender is mentioned in the law regarding public participation and the establishment of a Scientific Advisory Board, there are **no specific provisions addressing gender inequality** in policy-making, and **gender is absent from the assessment of National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs)**.

In contrast, the **EU Adaptation Strategy** acknowledges that climate impacts are not gender-neutral, highlighting the different adaptive capabilities of men and women and the need to consider social inequalities exacerbated by climate change. However, the **strategy falls short** in adequately addressing gender disparities in proposed actions and fails to sufficiently elaborate on enhancing resilience for vulnerable populations, such as those in the care sector, which has become evident during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the document "Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Adaptation: A DIY Manual²", published in September 2023 by the **EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change** as a living document, the word "gender" is mentioned only once, without explicitly stating its relevance or providing any guidelines. In the annual report on the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change (Activity Report published in May 2024³), the word "gender" does not appear anywhere in the document.

Among the initiatives highlighted in the "**Report on Gender Equality in the EU**" (European Commission, 2024), aimed at achieving equal participation across different sectors of the economy, it is worth mentioning the "**Women in the Blue Economy**" call supported by the European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund. The objective of this call is to help increase the participation of women in various sectors of the Blue Economy, including fisheries, aquaculture, shipbuilding, maritime transport, offshore renewable energy, blue bioeconomy, etc., across the European sea basins. One of the main outcomes of the projects is the enhanced knowledge and data on gender equality in the blue economy. These projects also facilitate deep, structural changes in sustainable blue economy sectors to promote the inclusion of women and provide them with the necessary tools and visibility to engage in the blue economy.

In summary, despite the **recognition** of the **importance** of enhancing gender-responsiveness in climate policy and the progress made in recent years, **integrating gender equality into EU climate objectives remains a pending issue.**

² Available at <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual>

³ Available at: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/eb7de6a7-b1b6-4a39-9c41-58db8d41d9e7_en?filename=ml-02-24-571-en-n.pdf

4 Gender Transformative FARCLIMATE Project Design and Implementation

4.1 Integration of Gender in Project Objectives

The conceptualization of FARCLIMATE has thoroughly considered alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically **Goal 5**, which focuses on achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls, and its **target 5.5** addressed by the Mission (European Commission, 2020c): *Ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic, and public life.*

The key components of Target 5.5 include:

- Promoting women's full and effective participation in leadership roles.
- Ensuring equal opportunities for women in political, economic, and public life.
- Addressing the barriers that prevent women from participating fully and equally in these areas.

Although some progress has been made according to the 2030 UN Agenda, the gender equality SDG score remains very high and varies greatly among EU countries (i.e., the gender overall employment gap is 20 in Italy, 11.4 in Spain, and 5.7 in France and Portugal; and the overall EU gender employment gap has only been reduced by 2.5 points in the last 10 years).

The focus of the FARCLIMATE project is on providing climate-resilient measures throughout the EU, with a strong commitment to **gender balance** and **equality**. In the **initial discussions** of the proposal, an essential aspect was the recognition that the current society, production and consumer habits, are strongly influenced by **gender**. For example, women report consuming a healthier and more sustainable diet (>70%) more frequently than men (<60%); food insecurity (moderate to severe levels) is higher in women than in men; women are at greater risk of poverty or social exclusion in all societal sectors (with a gap of 1.7 percentage points to the disadvantage of women in education, income, and traditional employment roles greatly influence this disadvantage); and opportunities in agriculture, forestry, and fishery systems are dependent on gender (farming, agriculture, and forestry are male-dominated professions, and although the majority of producers in developing countries are women, rural women are a minority in decision-making and planning activities, particularly in these sectors).

As there are factual differences in the factors affecting men and women, the **inclusion of gender-sensitive indicators and metrics** was considered from the project's design phase. Data will be collected and analysed, broken down by sex, age, and other socioeconomic factors (such as country, income, education level, or cultural parameters such as religion). This will lead to an in-depth understanding of the needs, behaviours, and attitudes of all genders, and the influence of socioeconomic factors, and will help researchers question gender norms and stereotypes, rethinking standards and reference models.

To ensure the design and implementation of a **Gender Transformative Approach (GTA)** tailored to the project's specific characteristics, the incorporation of a specific task (**T1.5**) focused on this goal was planned.

4.2 Building on the consortium capacities and experience

FARCLIMATE brings together leading experts in Knowledge Theory (UVIGO), Environmental Sciences (CTA), Forestry (CESEFOR), Agroecology (ULIEGE), Marketing and Business (UVIGO), Sustainability (IUCN, CERTH, CTA), Political Sciences (UVIGO, FUNDAO), Computer Science (INV), Fishing Sciences (FUNDAMAR), Educational and

Empowerment Sciences (C4G, UVIGO, GGG, ENOLL, CERTH, LAUREA), Living Labs (ENOLL, CERTH, LAUREA), Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CTA, ENOLL, CERTH, LAUREA), Data Visualization (INV), Behavioural Sciences (UNL) and Gender Sciences (IUCN & INV). This unique consortium has **multidisciplinary** and **complementary backgrounds, knowledge, and skills**, and joins research institutions, SMEs, NGOs, and public entities, making the FARCLIMATE consortium capable of achieving the challenging objectives that have been set.

Regarding the consortium's capacities and experiences related to **gender**, a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** is integrated into all the Research and Technology Organizations (RTOs), higher education institutions (HES), and public organizations participating in FARCLIMATE: III GEP Universidade de Vigo (UVIGO), GEP LIÈGE Université (ULIEGE), Gender Equality Plan Nova University Lisbon (UNL), the Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment Policy (IUCN), Plano para Igualdade (FUNDAO), I Gender Equality Plan (CESEFOR).

For decades, **IUCN** has been a **leading authority on gender-environment issues**, creating knowledge and raising awareness about the vital connections between gender equality and environmental outcomes. The Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment Policy of IUCN mandates gender-responsive actions across its programs and projects, shaping collaborations, strategies, and global impacts. IUCN has long been committed to addressing knowledge gaps on gender and climate change. In this context, the launch of **The Gender and Environment Resource Center**⁴ stands out, as it supports numerous projects aimed at advancing gender equality and women's empowerment within natural resource management activities.

Among the work carried out and programs executed in recent years, it is worth noting that IUCN has supported more than two dozen countries in developing **national climate change gender action plans (ccGAPs)**, which build on a country's national climate change policy, strategy, or plan – identifying gender gaps and gender-responsive actions across each priority sector to enhance rights-based, gender-responsive outcomes. Their work is reflected in **reports** such as "Gender and National Climate Planning: Gender Integration in the Revised Nationally Determined Contributions" (IUCN, 2021) and "The Art of Implementation: Gender Strategies Transforming National and Regional Climate Change Decision Making" (IUCN, 2012), which are undoubtedly **reference documents** in the **field of gender and climate change**.

Additionally, it is worth highlighting the experience of the partner **FUNDAMAR**, part of the **REDMAR network** for the exchange of experiences that favours the interrelation of all types of entities linked to the fishing sector, with the aim of promoting **equal opportunities between women and men**, encouraging boarding experiences of women with degrees in maritime fishing training, consolidating the network, and promoting the exchange of good practices in matters of equality, safety on board, and the environment. FUNDAMAR and FUNPROMAR created the brand **SEREAS**⁵ in 2017, as a project aimed at **raising awareness** about the **role of women** within the **extractive and transformative sector of seafood products**. Both foundations represent the collective occupations of the sea, whose women protagonists are an essential part of the sector's intangible heritage. The objective is to disseminate and value the testimonies of women workers in the sea-industry sector, as well as to preserve their stories, contribute, and provide solid sources of information to shape the forgotten history, creating characters to recover the memory of women's work from the past to the present. Also, FUNDAMAR launched in 2018 the "Strategy for the Promotion of the Social Economy in the Industrial Fishing Sector" (E ESO / PES) for the promotion and motivation of employment niches within the social economy in the field of industrial fishing and the creation of the first observatory of the social economy in the fishing sector, which includes shellfish harvesting organizations. Finally, it is worth highlighting their key role in promoting

⁴ <https://genderandenvironment.org/>

⁵ <https://sereasdomar.org/>

information and awareness campaigns for the integration of the **gender perspective** in the **prevention of occupational risks** in the fishing sector.

4.3 Gender transformation in the actions of the FARCLIMATE project

The implementation of FARCLIMATE's GTA starts with the recognition that it is a **process**, defined based on **core recommendations** that introduce **gender perspectives** and establish **general guidelines**. These are then followed by specific actions that the different activities of the project must consider.

The guiding directives that form the umbrella of GTA are as follows:

- **Ensure balanced and equal-opportunity participation** of women and men in work teams involved in the **execution** of the project, across all organizational levels, decision-making, management, and operations.
- **Ensure** that **women** and **men participate equally** in the **information-gathering processes** carried out for monitoring and evaluating the project (such as surveys, interviews, or other information-gathering techniques).
- **Ensure** that **women** and **men can access and participate** in the **resources/services** provided by the **activities** implemented in the project on an equal basis.
- **Include indicators** to measure the **integration** of the **gender perspective** in the processes related to the implementation of the project (for example, data disaggregated by sex).
- **Contract suppliers/companies** committed to **gender equality**. For example, companies/entities recognized for their commitment to equality, with equality measures integrated into their operations, and with demonstrable experience in gender equality.
- **Ensure** the **use** of **inclusive** and **non-sexist language** and **imagery** in all project materials (documentary and audiovisual), on the website, in project-related messages sent through social media, and at all communication events associated with the project. For example, feature pioneering women/female workers/female entrepreneurs in male-dominated sectors.
- **Highlight** the **commitment to gender equality** of the **organizations** involved in the project.

The FARCLIMATE **GTA** provides the **context** and **aligns** with the **Ethical Issues Assessment**, as reflected in deliverable **D1.4** (submitted on 31/01/2024), which covers the assessment of ethical issues in the FARCLIMATE project and how they will be addressed throughout. This document describes the three intertwined principles of **Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion**, which will help FARCLIMATE promote **fairness** and **justice** in the activities conducted within the work packages, in the local communities hosting the case studies, and by guiding FARCLIMATE results in European adaptation to climate change. Overall, FARCLIMATE will seek the involvement of diverse participants without unfair discrimination based on age, disability, race, gender, sexual orientation, religion, belief, or ideology, among other factors. Everyone involved in society must be heard and considered in climate change adaptation. As **bias** is a concern, D1.4 describes actions to be taken, such as ensuring a balanced composition of stakeholders.

The FARCLIMATE **communication strategy**, developed in task T8.1 and reflected in deliverable **D8.1** (submitted on 08/04/2024) of WP8, is summarized in the motto "together, we can all work for a climate-resilient future." This strategy integrates the GTA with communication guidelines that reinforce an active, participatory, and positive approach conducive to promoting diversity, inclusion, and equity.

The definition of the FARCLIMATE GTA is framed within the work carried out in **WP1 - Project Management**, which has among its key objectives the formation of a strong organizational structure to achieve effective and result-driven management, as well as to ensure the achievement of objectives, timely delivery of all technical reports to the European Commission, and identification of risks with the application of corrective action plans

when necessary. The **Project Management Guidelines** described in deliverable **D1.1** (submitted on 29/12/2023) serve as the foundational document outlining the comprehensive project governance and management structure for FARCLIMATE. The **management structures** detailed in D1.1, including the Project Coordinator (PC), the General Assembly, the Steering Committee (SC), the Innovation & Exploitation Board (IEB), Work Package Leaders (WPL), and the External Advisory Board (EAB), are essential for monitoring compliance, overseeing project progress, conducting risk management, and facilitating innovation transfer. These structures, together with the **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** considered throughout all the WPs to ensure the achievement of established objectives, **will be critically examined** as part of the monitoring and evaluation process described in detail in section 5.

The **WP2 – Case Studies Development and Stakeholder Interaction** concentrates on the **conceptual, strategic, methodological**, and **operational basis** of the FARCLIMATE case studies. As outlined in deliverable **D2.1 Methodological Approach for FARCLIMATE** (submitted on 30/04/2024), these case studies serve as the cornerstone of the FARCLIMATE project. Consequently, the Living Lab methodology introduced in T2.1 and implemented in T2.4 serves as the primary catalyst for driving the project's diverse activities. Task 2.2 Selection of Case Studies not only presented the selected cases but also solicited feedback from Task 2.1, thereby informing potential case study candidates about the Living Lab methodology. Task 2.3 Stakeholder Management Strategy is directly responsible for shaping the stakeholder management approach for the case studies, ensuring alignment with both the GTA and the Living Lab methodology.

Specifically, T2.1 establishes a significant portion of the strategic context for FARCLIMATE's outlined work program:

- **Initial engagement** with all relevant stakeholders in each region, establishing management mechanisms (WP2).
- **Establishment of Living Labs** to facilitate co-creation, testing, and scaling-up of innovative activities in real-life environments (WP2).

Within each case study, the core users will form a panel, underscoring the importance for FARCLIMATE partners to ensure its equitable representation across diverse quadruple helix groups. Furthermore, examination of these groups should encompass considerations such as gender, age, and ethnicity where applicable. Constructing such a panel is intricate and time-intensive, requiring FARCLIMATE Living Labs to cultivate trust with stakeholders. This necessitates adherence to ethical standards, customization of work protocols, and maintenance of transparent communication and feedback channels. It's noteworthy that the FARCLIMATE Living Lab Methodology and subsequent training **integrate principles and KPIs for gender-inclusive Living Labs** as delineated by the GILL project. Additionally, as delineated in D2.1, FARCLIMATE prioritizes the preparation and dissemination of educational materials to all, irrespective of gender, age, or socioeconomic status. Consequently, training programs will ensure an equal 50% gender distribution among participants (WP4, WP5).

Once the initial **selection of case studies**, as described in **deliverable 2.2** (submitted on 30/04/2024), has been completed, the **GTA** must constitute a **cross-cutting element** in defining the **specific interventions** designed for each case study. These interventions should be **adapted to cultural and social contexts** and aimed at effectively and equitably addressing needs. It is essential to bear in mind that **culturally sensitive approaches** rely on awareness and accommodation of the **local context**, requiring active participation from the teams responsible for coordinating the case studies.

At the **second meeting of the General Assembly**, to be held on June 6-7 in Fundão (Portugal), the INV team will present the approach and guidelines of the **FARCLIMATE GTA**. The aim is to establish a **common understanding** and discuss with the consortium the **specific characteristics** of the different case studies. This initial action will be reinforced by the activity planned in Task 4.4, involving representatives from the case

studies, within the framework of the **Open Living Lab Day (OLLD24)** to be held on September 25-27, 2024, in Timisoara, Romania.

It is worth noting that the emphasis on inclusiveness and participation described in D1.4 for the interaction of case study stakeholders with **WP3**, **WP4**, and **WP5** research, technical innovations, and training is integrated with and complemented by the GTA described in this document. As outlined in relation to the Ethical Issues Assessment, WP3 activities analyse climate adaptation strategies from social impact and consumer perspectives, aiming to promote climate adaptation strategies that support more vulnerable or disadvantaged groups, thereby promoting more equitable climate adaptation. Specifically, the socioeconomic impact in T3.4 (e.g., effects on the labour market, well-being, inclusive work, the role of women) and the consumer perspective (T3.5) are addressed. Training activities (WP4) also target different types of stakeholders to build capabilities and empower them to face climate change adaptation. The stakeholders participating in WP2 will also contribute to and review the sector-specific innovations to be developed in WP5.

Furthermore, based on the focus on inclusiveness, diversity, and equity of the previous activities, the results sought by FARCLIMATE and specified in **WP6** (business and management models, policy recommendations, and the European Climate-Resilient Communities Network) and **WP7** (Transformation Hub) will aim for a fair, inclusive, and gender-transformative adaptation to climate change, in addition to the economic and technical aspects. Acknowledging that women's leadership is key to climate action, inspiring stories of "**Women shaping climate action**" will be central to the concept of the section "Toward a climate-resilient future together" in the Transformation Hub section.

5 Monitoring and Evaluation, and Learning!

New ways of working require a **broader understanding** of the **outcomes** and **impacts** we aim to achieve, as well as new methods of measuring and learning from our efforts. A **gender-transformative monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) system** should extend beyond tracking participation in program activities to assessing the impact of program interventions. Moreover, integrating participation, joint learning, and reflection processes into the monitoring and evaluation of adaptation programs is essential to maximize their effectiveness.

A participatory and gender-responsive MEL system can provide a platform for local stakeholders, empowering them to express their needs. This approach allows the program to facilitate **ongoing joint learning** and **reflection**, including the collaborative development of indicators, which is particularly important for adaptation due to the community's evolving needs. Integrating participation, joint learning, and reflection processes into the monitoring and evaluation of adaptation programs ensures these efforts are as **effective** as possible.

The MEL system monitors and documents **gender achievements** in the program to generate **critical knowledge** and **evidence**, which can be used to advocate for and contribute to an enabling environment for gender-transformative policy at community, local, national, and global levels.

The **INV team** will act as the **gender focal point**, with responsibilities to support gender-mainstreaming as well as MEL coordination. Monitoring activities will be developed, applying the principle of ensuring that women and men participate equally in the information-gathering processes carried out for monitoring and evaluating the project, in the context of the **General Assembly meetings**, where each partner will present the interim results and data achieved in the form of an oral presentation and electronic files containing all details. The evaluation will pay special attention to the performance of the management structures and the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) considered throughout all the WPs to ensure the achievement of established

objectives, critically evaluating "how far along is GTA FARCLIMATE?" on a scale of **aware – engaged – integrated**.

Finally, the lessons learned during the implementation process will be integrated into the **final version** of the GTA (**D1.6**), which will be delivered at the end of the project (**M48**).

6 Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis of how **gender aspects** and **dimensions** are being addressed in **EU climate policies** has shown that, despite the recognition of the importance of enhancing gender-responsiveness in climate policy and the progress made in recent years, integrating gender equality into EU climate objectives remains an **unresolved issue**.

The Gender Transformative Approach (**GTA**) of **FARCLIMATE** has been designed to **tackle this challenge**, using South-North cooperation -specifically, the lessons learned from the implementation of GTAs mentioned throughout this document- as a significant starting point.

The purpose of this document, envisioned as a **living document**, is to present the harmonized framework for gender transformation within the project. It describes the guidelines that establish the fundamental aspects, criteria, conceptual foundations, and processes that the various activities must consider. Beginning with a brief overview of the concepts, key milestones, and challenges related to gender in the context of climate adaptation, the following sections outlined the main characteristics of FARCLIMATE's GTA, from project design to implementation, as well as the system designed for monitoring, evaluation, and learning.

Conceived as a **process**, a **lens** that enables us to identify the most effective strategies for implementing an intervention across the **gender continuum**, with the aim of transforming gender norms and power relations in each specific context where we operate, **thinking about the role of a GTA** requires the consortium to **honestly self-reflect** and assess their openness and preparedness to facilitate systemic change.

As we have emphasized, by definition, **GTAs mean change for the implementing organizations** and how we work. This **sincere reflection** and **critical perspective** when evaluating the project's progress are the **fundamental pillars** to ensure that the project's learnings provide **valuable lessons** -of **success** or **failure**- that can be incorporated into future efforts and actions in the European context.

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Annex 1. Glossary of gender-related terms

Agency

Individual and collective capacities (knowledge and skills), attitudes, critical reflection, assets, actions, and access to services.

Gender

Gender refers to the culturally defined roles, responsibilities, attributes, and entitlements associated with being (or being perceived as) a woman or man in a given context, along with the power relations between and among women and men. Most gender systems are deeply patriarchal, ascribing greater value to what is considered masculine than to what is considered feminine. 'Socially constructed' means that these roles and attributes are not innate or natural but are created by society. Consequently, they can also be modified or changed.

Gender diverse

The term gender-diverse is used to refer to persons whose gender identity, including their gender expression, is at odds with what is perceived as being the gender norm in a particular context at a particular point in time, including those who do not place themselves in the male/female binary.

Gender equality

Gender equality refers to equal outcomes for women, men, girls, boys and gender-diverse people.

Gender Equality Plan

Strategic framework implemented by organizations to promote gender equality, addressing disparities and fostering an inclusive environment. These plans outline specific actions and measures to achieve gender balance, ensure equal opportunities, eliminate discrimination, and support diversity across various organizational levels and activities.

Gender equity

Gender equity refers to fairness: the process of levelling the playing field to achieve gender equality. Gender-transformative approaches are a way to operationalize gender equity, with the goal of achieving gender equality through intentional and additional measures.

Gender mainstreaming

A strategy for making the needs and interests of all genders an integral part of the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of programmes, policies and organizational processes, so that everyone has the opportunity to benefit equally, and inequality is not perpetuated. This is a potential route to transforming gendered outcomes at all levels, but in practice, there is a risk of it being reduced to a bureaucratic process, that avoids engaging with power inequalities.

Gender non-conforming

Gender non-conforming refers to gender expressions other than male or female.

Gender norms

Gender norms are deeply entrenched and widely held beliefs and expectations about gender roles that govern human behaviours and practices within a particular social context and at a particular point in time.

Gender roles

Gender roles are the expected roles, including behaviours, activities, and responsibilities, associated with each sex. Gender socialization processes by which individuals (especially children and adolescents) internalize gender norms. Internalization refers to a process of learning what norms are, understanding why they are of value or make sense, and accepting the norm as one's own. It is a complex and ongoing process, which begins at birth, continues through childhood, and intensifies during adolescence until individuals have internalized traditional gender identities and begun to perpetuate them to future generations. Gender norms are learned early in life and evidence suggests that by age 3, children begin to develop a sense of gender identity.

Gender stereotypes

Generalizations about the characteristics of a group of people based on gender.

Gender integration continuum

Framework that helps us to understand the process of integrating gendered approaches in policies, programmes and activities and to better identify strategies to set an intervention aiming for a gender transformative approach into motion. Gender integration can helpfully be viewed across a continuum, from gender-discriminatory, gender-blind, or gender-sensitive, to gender-responsive or gender-transformative.

Gender-responsive programming

Gender-responsive programming deliberately responds to the needs of adults and children of different genders, assessing the gendered context and taking measures to actively address specific needs.

Gender-responsive just transition

A gender-responsive just transition refers to the process of developing green sectors while ensuring a fair transition for the workforce and enterprises, with a specific focus on establishing equality of opportunity and treatment for both women and men from the beginning. This approach aims to prevent sectoral and occupational segregation, eliminate wage and skills gaps, promote inclusive social dialogue, improve working conditions, and enhance social protection. It also seeks to improve skills, reduce health and safety risks that disproportionately affect women, and facilitate the formalization of informal economy jobs held by women. Ultimately, it ensures that women are not left behind in the shift to a low-carbon and sustainable economy, recognizing and leveraging their essential contributions to green growth and sustainable development.

Gender-responsive social protection interventions

Gender-responsive social protection interventions may aim to effectively reach girls, boys, women and men specifically to achieve gender equality outcomes.

Gender transformative approach

A transformative approach promotes gender equality by fostering critical examination of inequalities and gender roles, norms and dynamics recognizing and strengthening positive norms that support equality and

an enabling environment promoting the relative position of women, girls and marginalized groups and transforming the underlying social structures, policies, systems and broadly held social norms that perpetuate and legitimize gender inequalities.

Gender-transformative programming

Gender-transformative programming actively aims to promote gender equality and women's and girls' outcomes as a primary objective, by deliberately tackling discriminatory and harmful gender norms, roles, structures and institutions that perpetuate gender inequalities and gendered risks in the long-term.

Gender-sensitive programming

Gender-sensitive programming acknowledges gender inequalities and may act on gender analysis insofar as needed to reach programme objectives but does not necessarily prioritize girls' and women's needs specifically or address structural causes of gender inequality.

Gender-based violence

An umbrella term for any harmful act perpetrated against a person's will based on socially ascribed (i.e., gender) differences between males and females. The term 'gender-based' underscores the fact that structural, gender-based power inequalities between males and females around the world place females at risk for multiple forms of violence. It includes acts that inflict physical, mental, or sexual harm or suffering, threats of such acts, coercion, and other deprivations of liberty, whether occurring in public or private life. The term is also used to describe some forms of sexual violence against males and/or targeted violence against LGBTQI+ populations when referencing violence related to gender-inequitable norms of masculinity and/or norms of gender identity.

Feminist approach

Feminist approaches seek to transform patriarchal power structures and to empower those disadvantaged by them: most often girls and women, but in some cases, also men and boys and people of non-conforming gender identities. Feminist approaches are one of the key conceptual foundations upon which gender-transformative approaches are built. Contemporary feminist approaches are intersectional—they take into account the way people experience multiple forms of discrimination and oppression based on different aspects of their identity (e.g. race, gender, class, disability, sexual orientation or gender identity).

Heteronormativity

Heteronormativity refers to the set of beliefs and practices that consider gender to be an absolute, unquestionable binary, and therefore describe and reinforce heterosexuality as a norm. It implies that people's gender, sex and sex characteristics are by nature and should always be aligned, and therefore heterosexuality is the only conceivable sexuality and the only way of being 'normal'.

Homophobia

Fear, unreasonable anger, intolerance or/and hatred directed towards homosexuality.

Intersectionality

A framework for understanding how aspects of a person's social and political identities combine to create different forms of discrimination and privilege. These identities include gender, race, ethnicity, ability, class, sexual orientation, gender identity, immigration status, and age among other issues.

Intimate partner violence

Physical, sexual or psychological acts by a current or former intimate partner that result or are likely to result in physical, sexual or psychological harm. For purposes of the SDG indicator, an intimate partner is generally defined as a husband, cohabiting sexual partner, or long-term, non-cohabiting, sexual partner, though some surveys include other romantic and 'dating' partners. 'Domestic violence' may refer to partner violence but may also encompass child or elder abuse, or abuse by any member of a household.

Masculinities

Masculinities are the patterns of behaviour and practice that reflect and reinforce the position of men and boys in the gender order. These patterns of behaviour and practice vary across cultural and social settings, within groups and networks, and across time. As part of the gender order, masculinity is defined in relation to femininity; indeed, rigidity about the binary distinction between masculinity and femininity and a resistance to greater fluidity is a core manifestation of patriarchy.

Non-binary

Gender identities that are neither "man" nor "woman".

Sex

Refers to biological characteristics (including genetic, hormonal, physiological, anatomical) that distinguish between male, female, and intersex (in humans) or hermaphrodite (in non-human animals).

Sexual violence in childhood

All forms of sexual victimization of a girl or a boy under 18 years of age, including sexual abuse and sexual exploitation, including forced, pressured, coerced, unwanted or unlawful sexual activity, or attempts to engage in such activity. Sexual activity may include sexual intercourse or other sex acts, contact or non-contact sexual abuse and harassment, as well as sexual exploitation, in person and online.

Sexism

Sexism is a system of beliefs around the fundamental nature of women and men and the roles they should play in society. Sexism manifests in gender roles and stereotypes that can rank one gender superior to the other.

Social protection

Social protection is broadly understood to refer to a set of policies and programmes aimed at preventing or protecting all people against poverty, vulnerability and social exclusion throughout their life course, with a particular emphasis towards vulnerable groups.

Structural discrimination

Structural or systemic discrimination occurs when an entire network of rules and practices disadvantages less empowered groups and serves to advantage the dominant groups.

Violence against women and girls

Any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women and girls, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life.

Annex 2. International Gender-Specific Environmental and Climate Commitments

1979 – Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)

CEDAW is the first international bill of women’s rights that looks into issues regarding rural development, and that addresses issues of resources, credit, education, the right to work and participation.

1992 – United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED)

Resulted in the Rio Declaration and Agenda 21 (1992) that recognize women as a major group in sustainable development and underline the importance of taking into account gender and social dimensions in environment, and the relevance of environmental issues for gender equality and women’s empowerment, respectively.

1992 –United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

It was adopted in 1992 in Rio de Janeiro. This international environmental agreement was, however, the only Rio Convention that did not make any reference to gender and social issues.

1992 –United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity:

It recognized the importance of a gender-specific approach in the conservation and sustainable management of natural resources.

1995 – Fourth United Nations Women’s Conference

Beijing Declaration and Beijing Platform for Action: Section K discusses the interface between Women and the Environment, and accordingly proposes strategic objectives and action points.

1997 – the Kyoto Protocol

It was an extension of the UNFCCC, specifically looking into climate change mitigation, but again no references to gender aspects.

2001 – COP7 in Marrakesh

UNFCCC parties have recognized gender equality and women’s participation, as important principles.

2010 – COP16 in Cancun

COP16 marked a pivotal moment in acknowledging that climate change does not affect all people equally. The Cancun Agreements emphasized the need for gender balance in climate change negotiations and decision-making processes. The agreements set a precedent for future COPs to continue and expand the integration of gender perspectives into climate policy.

2011 – COP17 in Durban

UNFCCC adopted Decision 5/CP.17 on Guidelines for National Adaptation Plans (NAPs) should be country-driven, participatory, with a gender-sensitive approach.

2012 – COP18 in Doha

UNFCCC adopted decision 23/ CP.18 on promoting gender balance and improving the participation of women in negotiations and in the representation of Parties in bodies established pursuant to the Convention or the Kyoto Protocol.

2014 – COP20 in Lima

UNFCCC adopted decision 18/ CP.20 requested the secretariat to prepare an Action Plan for the development of the two-year work program on gender, also known as the Lima Work Programme on Gender. As part of this process, the secretariat maps decisions and implementation on gender and climate change, and compiles these for the COPs.

2015 – COP21 in Paris

In the UNFCCC Paris Agreement, gender aspects were included in Preamble, Adaptation, Capacity Building; but not in the sections on mitigation, technology development and transfer, or financing. In decision 1/CP.21, an Annex, Parties acknowledge:

...climate change is a common concern of humankind, Parties should...respect, promote and consider their respective obligations on human rights, the right to health, the rights of indigenous peoples, local communities, migrants, children, persons with disabilities and people in vulnerable situations and the right to development, as well as gender equality, empowerment of women and intergenerational equity.

2015 – Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction

Adopted at the World Conference on Disaster Risk Reduction, it calls for stronger gender, age, and disability perspectives in policies and practices; promotion of women's leadership; women's participation in DRR; re-sourcing and implementing gender sensitive DRR; and adequate capacity building measures for women's empowerment and livelihoods.

2015 – The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development:

The Agenda has a strong gender focus in SDG5 (achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls) – with nine specific targets and gender-sensitive targets for most other SDGs. Also, SDG 10 (reducing inequality) is relevant in this context. All SDGs, including SDG 13 (climate action), have important gender-equality implications and require a gender-sensitive approach to meet the 2030 targets.

2016 – COP22 in Marrakech

UNFCCC Parties reviewed progress made toward the goals of gender balance and the implementation of gender-responsive climate policy and decided to continue and enhance the Lima work programme on gender for a period of 3 years. Decision 21/ CP.22 was adopted by the COP: a call for submissions on views on possible elements of the gender action plan to be developed under the Lima work programme on gender.

2017 – COP23 in Bonn

UNFCCC Parties adopted a new roadmap to incorporate gender equality and women's empowerment in climate change discourse and actions. The creation of a Gender Action Plan was agreed upon by the Parties, to bolster the role of women in climate action.

2018 – COP24 in Katowice

UNFCCC Parties adopted the Paris Implementation Guidelines with explicit reference to the importance of gender responsiveness, gender balance, taking into account social aspects, and including traditional/indigenous/local knowledge in several areas: the Nationally Agreed Contributions (NDCs), Adaptation Communication, Finance, Technology Framework, Transparency Framework, and Compliance. This context is also promoted in the work of the Subsidiary Body on Scientific and Technological Advice and the Subsidiary Body on Implementation to use a gender-specific approach, including in the review of the Lima Work Programme on Gender in 2019.

2018 – The UNFCCC Gender Action Plan (GAP)

The GAP sets out priority areas of adaptation; mitigation; and the means of implementation including finance, technology development and transfer, capacity building as the activities that will help achieve the gender mainstreaming objective in climate change. These range from increasing knowledge and capacities of women and men through workshops and information exchanges, to pursuing the full, equal and meaningful participation of diverse women in national delegations. Also prioritized was the need to increase integration of the gender considerations into the areas of work of all Parties to the Convention; and to increase climate-related financial resources that integrate gender priorities and reflect the needs of women and girls. Lastly, the GAP seeks to improve tracking of the implementation of the gender-related decisions.

2019 – COP25 in Madrid

The enhanced Lima Work Programme on Gender and its Gender Action Plan (GAP) were adopted. This plan outlines a five-year strategy to advance gender-responsive climate policy and action. It focuses on five priority areas: capacity-building, gender balance, coherence, gender-responsive implementation, and monitoring and reporting.

2019 - European Green Deal

The European Green Deal, launched by the European Commission, includes a commitment to a just transition that leaves no one behind, explicitly recognizing the importance of gender equality. It aims to integrate gender considerations across its climate and environmental policies, ensuring that women benefit equally from the green transition.

2021 - COP26 in Glasgow

The Glasgow Climate Pact, adopted at COP26 in Glasgow, underscored the importance of gender-responsive climate policies and the role of women in climate action. It called for continued support to the UNFCCC Gender Action Plan and recognized the need for enhanced support for vulnerable communities, including women and girls.

2021 - Generation Equality Forum

Launched by UN Women, the Generation Equality Forum held in Mexico City and Paris marked the 25th anniversary of the Beijing Platform for Action. The forum emphasized the intersection of gender equality and climate justice, resulting in commitments from governments, civil society, and the private sector to promote gender equality within environmental and climate initiatives.

2022 - IPCC Sixth Assessment Report

Among the elements that the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defined as the core elements of a just transition in the Sixth Assessment Report is gender-specific policies that promote equitable outcomes.

2023 - COP28 in Dubai

As part of COP28's Gender Equality Day, the COP28 Presidency launched the Gender-Responsive Just Transitions & Climate Action Partnership, which was endorsed by 68 Parties. The Partnership includes a package of commitments on finance, data and equal opportunities. This partnership is aiming to build upon progress made through the enhanced UN Climate Change Lima Work Programme and its Gender Action Plan. Moreover, on the eve of COP28, the Global Conference on Gender and Environmental Data resulted in an urgent call for action to increase the collection and use of gender and environmental data to push gender-responsive climate and environmental action on a global scale.

Annex 3. Additional Resources and References for Gender Transformation and Climate Adaptation

Institutions and Organizations

Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) - GENDER Impact Platform: <https://gender.cgiar.org/>

Convention of biological diversity – Gender and biodiversity: <https://www.cbd.int/gender>

European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE): <https://eige.europa.eu/>

International Institute for Environment and Development (iied): <https://www.iied.org/>

International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) - Gender and Environment Resource Center: <https://genderandenvironment.org/>

The Global Center on Adaptation: <https://gca.org/>

The Interagency Gender Working Group: <https://www.igwg.org/>

The Nature Conservancy: <https://www.nature.org/en-us/>

UN Environment – Gender and Climate Action: <https://www.unep.org/topics/gender/gender-and-climate-action>

UN Women: <https://www.unwomen.org/>

United Nations Climate Change – Gender: <https://unfccc.int/gender>

Women Engage for a Common Future (WECF): <https://www.wecf.org/>

Women’s Environment & Development Organization (WEDO): <https://wedo.org/>

World Meteorological Organization – Gender Equality: <https://wmo.int/about-wmo/gender-equality>

World Resources Institute – Gender: <https://www.wri.org/equitable-development/gender>

Guidelines and Reports

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Kwauk, C. and Casey, O. 2021. A New Green Learning Agenda: Approaches to Quality Education for Climate Action. Brookings Institution, Washington, D.C.

Programme (UNDP), New York, NY, USA, 69 pp.

UN Women. 2023. The Climate–Care Nexus: Addressing the linkages between climate change and women’s and girls’ unpaid care, domestic and communal work. New York.

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). 2010: Gender, Climate Change and Community-Based Adaptation. A Guidebook for Designing and Implementing Gender-Sensitive Community-Based Adaptation Programmes and Projects, United Nations Development

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). 2022. How Just Transition can help deliver the Paris Agreement. New York.

United Nations Economic and Social Council. 2022a. Report of the Secretary General: Achieving gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls in the context of climate change, environmental and disaster risk reduction policies and programmes. E/CN.6/2022/3.

United Nations Economic and Social Council. 2022b. Achieving gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls in the context of climate change, environmental and disaster risk reduction policies and programmes. Agreed conclusions. E/CN.6/2022/L.7.

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). 2022. Dimensions and examples of the gender-differentiated impacts of climate change, the role of women as agents of change and opportunities for women. Synthesis report by the secretariat.

Women’s Budget Group and Wen. 2022. A green and care economy – Key messages.

Statistical Sources

Gender Climate Tracker: <https://genderclimatetracker.org/>

EIGE - Gender Statistics Database: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs>

Statistical Office of the European Union Eurostat: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>